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The percentage of ICT services exports in total trade

Decreased on average by -6.89% between 2016 and 2022

The variable "ICT services exports, % total trade" represents the percentage of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) services exports relative to the total trade in goods and services of a country. ICT services include the provision of services such as software development, IT consulting, data management, telecommunications services, and other digital services. This percentage serves as an indicator of the economic importance of the ICT sector within a country's foreign trade. A higher value indicates an economy that is more oriented towards the export of technological and digital services, suggesting a high level of expertise in technological and digital innovation. Conversely, a lower value might indicate a greater dependence on the export of tangible goods or traditional services. The importance of monitoring this variable lies in the fact that the ICT sector is increasingly considered a key driver for economic development and global competitiveness. A high share of ICT exports reflects a country's ability to generate added value in the digital sector, fostering economic growth and improving the trade balance. Additionally, it allows for the assessment of the impact of government policies aimed at encouraging technological and digital development. In summary, "ICT services exports, % total trade" is a crucial measure for understanding the role of the technology sector in a country's economy, highlighting its integration into global markets through the export of ICT services.

The Percentage of ICT services exports in total trade in 2022. The data on ICT services exports as a percentage of total trade presents a diverse and revealing landscape of the economic specialization of different countries in the Information and Communication Technology sector. The ranking is led by nations such as Cyprus, India, Ireland, and Israel, which reach 100% in ICT exports relative to their total trade. This means that the entire export of these countries is dominated by digital services, suggesting an economy strongly oriented towards the technology sector. These countries have been able to capitalize on their technological expertise, creating favorable ecosystems for the development of digital services and their commercialization on a global scale. In Europe, Ireland represents an emblematic case: it has attracted numerous technology multinationals thanks to a favorable tax environment and advanced infrastructure. Israel, often dubbed the "Startup Nation," is known for its capacity for technological innovation and a thriving ICT sector that drives the local economy, fueled by a robust educational system and significant investments in research and development. Countries like Finland, with a percentage of 93.8%, stand out for their commitment to developing advanced technologies. Finland, historically associated with the success of companies like Nokia, continues to be a leader in digital innovation and high-quality services, especially in areas such as artificial intelligence and connectivity. Moving down the ranking, unexpected countries appear in the higher ranks, such as Kuwait (70.6%) and Ukraine (60.5%). For Kuwait, the data suggests a growing economic diversification, an attempt to reduce dependence on oil by investing in innovative sectors.

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Ukraine, on the other hand, has emerged in recent years as a major hub for software development and IT outsourcing in Eastern Europe, thanks in part to a large pool of highly skilled professionals at competitive costs. Costa Rica and Armenia, with percentages of 55.1% and 53.5% respectively, represent examples of small economies that have made the ICT sector a pillar of their growth strategies. In particular, Costa Rica has attracted many technology companies thanks to its political stability and skilled workforce, while Armenia has become an important hub for startups and IT companies in the Caucasus region. Countries like Romania (51%) and Sweden (47.8%) show how the ICT sector is a central element in their economies. Romania is known as a key destination for IT offshoring services, while Sweden is distinguished by its innovation ecosystem that has given rise to globally successful technology companies like Spotify and Klarna. An interesting aspect is the presence of developing economies such as the Philippines (45.3%), Sri Lanka (45.2%), and Kenya (29.3%), which are using the ICT sector as a growth engine. The Philippines, for example, is a world leader in Business Process Outsourcing (BPO), while Kenya is often considered the "Silicon Savannah" due to its vibrant tech scene and innovative startups. On the other hand, the relatively low percentage of countries like China (18%), the United States (16.5%), and Germany (15.8%) might be surprising, but it should be interpreted in the context of diversified economies where the trade in tangible goods remains predominant. Even though these nations are global leaders in the technology sector, their overall exports include a wide variety of industrial and manufacturing products, thus reducing the percentage share of ICT exports relative to the total. Italy, with 11.7%, reflects a reality where the ICT sector has a growing role, but is not yet central compared to other traditional economic sectors like manufacturing. Although Italy has a significant number of innovative companies and tech startups, its economy is still dominated by the export of tangible goods, such as luxury products, machinery, and foodstuffs. At the bottom of the ranking, we find countries like Mexico (0%) and Angola (0.4%), where ICT exports represent an insignificant share of total trade. This indicates economies still heavily dependent on traditional sectors or natural resources. In Mexico, despite a growing technology industry, exports are dominated by manufactured products, especially in the automotive sector. The figure of 1.3% for Thailand and 1.2% for Iran reflects economies characterized by a strong focus on different industries, such as tourism for Thailand and energy resources for Iran. In these economies, the ICT sector has not yet emerged as a leading player in exports. These data collectively highlight how the share of ICT exports in total trade can provide a clear indication of the degree of digitalization and the economic structure of various countries. The leading countries in this ranking have developed technological competencies that not only meet domestic demand but are also highly competitive on an international level. However, the presence of emerging countries at the top of the ranking suggests that the ICT sector offers opportunities even for less developed economies that can leverage outsourcing, digitalization, and innovation to accelerate their economic growth. In conclusion, the variable "ICT services exports as a percentage of total trade" represents not only an indicator of a nation's technological capacity but also a reflection of its economic priorities and competitive positioning in the global context. The analysis of these data highlights the growing importance of digital services in international trade dynamics and how these are redefining the global economic landscape, providing new opportunities for both advanced and emerging economies.

The Percentage of ICT services exports in total trade between 2016 and 2022. The analysis of data on the percentage of ICT services exports in total trade between 2016 and 2022 offers a snapshot of the profound economic transformations that many countries have experienced in terms of digitalization, technological development, and international trade strategies. Some countries have

recorded spectacular growth, while others have experienced sharp declines, suggesting structural changes in their economies. Namibia emerges as one of the most surprising cases, with an increase in the percentage of ICT exports in total trade of 1800%, rising from 0.1% in 2016 to 1.9% in 2022. This figure, though starting from a very low base, reflects the country's attempt to diversify its economy and invest in high-value-added sectors like ICT. Similarly, Saudi Arabia recorded growth of 1733.33%, rising from 0.3% to 5.5%. This growth is indicative of the country's efforts to reduce its dependence on oil, promoting the development of the technology sector and advancing projects like "Vision 2030," which aims to digitize and modernize the Saudi economy. Countries like Qatar and Turkey have seen growth rates of 577.78% and 466.67%, respectively. Qatar, already a major hub for ICT infrastructure, has significantly increased its weight in this sector, while Turkey, despite a complex geopolitical context, has managed to strengthen the role of ICT exports, benefiting from a thriving tech sector. Among European countries, Lithuania and Belarus stand out for their strong growth, at 170.27% and 140.99%, respectively. Lithuania, already known for its solid digital infrastructure, has consolidated its role as a technology hub in the Baltic region. Belarus, despite political difficulties and international sanctions, has seen significant growth thanks to the IT industry, which represents one of the few remaining avenues for economic development in the country. Another emblematic case is Finland, with growth of 50.08%, consolidating its role as one of the world leaders in technological innovation. This figure reflects the continued development of advanced technologies and Finland's leadership in areas such as 5G and artificial intelligence. The growth of countries like China (100%) and Japan (166.67%) highlights how Asian powers are increasing their presence in the global trade of ICT services, although China already starts from a solid base. Japan's growth suggests a transition towards an increasingly digital economy, driven by an aging population and the need for advanced technological solutions. On the other hand, some countries have seen a significant reduction in the share of ICT exports in total trade. A dramatic example is Nepal, which recorded a decline of 80.48%, falling from 82.5% in 2016 to 16.1% in 2022. This decline can be attributed to a series of factors, including the lack of investment in the technology sector, brain drain, and political instability. The situation in Nepal mirrors that of many developing countries that, despite initially investing in the ICT sector, have been unable to sustain long-term growth. Similarly, Costa Rica experienced a 44.9% contraction, from 100% in 2016 to 55.1% in 2022. Although the country remains an important exporter of digital services, the increasing global competitiveness in this sector has made it more difficult to maintain such a high share in total trade. In Europe, Sweden saw a significant contraction of 34.34%, from 72.8% to 47.8%. Despite remaining one of the most technologically advanced countries, the decline may reflect greater economic diversification and increased international competition in the ICT sector. Switzerland also recorded a dramatic decline of 46.88%, probably due to a growing focus on other high-value-added sectors. Other countries that have experienced sharp contractions include Uganda (64.71%), Senegal (73.73%), and Burundi (82.62%). These countries, which initially focused on ICT as a development engine, have faced economic difficulties, lack of investment, and political instability, all factors that have prevented sustainable expansion of the sector. Italy recorded a contraction of 24.52%, from 15.5% to 11.7%. This data highlights how, despite some growth in tech companies and digital startups, the ICT sector still fails to represent a significant share of Italian foreign trade. The Italian economy remains strongly oriented towards the export of tangible goods, especially in the manufacturing and agri-food sectors. France and Germany, with contractions of 22.81% and 17.28% respectively, show a similar trend. Despite being world leaders in technology and innovation, their ICT exports have been unable to keep pace with the increase in global competitiveness and the diversification of their economies. The most significant collapse is observed in countries like Tajikistan (95.92%) and Benin (89.44%), which have been unable to sustain the initial growth in the ICT sector. In many cases, these countries have faced problems related to the lack of infrastructure, low technological penetration, and general economic

difficulties, which have limited their ability to export digital services. In summary, the data shows that the ICT sector is continually evolving and reflects the complex dynamics of global economies. Countries that have successfully invested in technological infrastructure and human capital have seen significant growth, consolidating their position in the international trade of digital services. Conversely, economies that have been unable to sustain such investments or that have experienced political and economic instability have seen their share of ICT exports dramatically reduced. These changes underline the importance of a long-term strategy for the development of the technology sector, which requires a mix of investments, favorable government policies, and a stable context to attract talent and capital.

Economic policies. Economic policies aimed at increasing the percentage of ICT services exports in total trade require an integrated and multidimensional approach. The growth of this sector depends on a combination of factors including investments in technological infrastructure, human capital development, tax incentives, access to international markets, and strong digital governance. First, one of the fundamental policies concerns the development of advanced digital infrastructure. To allow ICT companies to grow and compete globally, it is essential to have an efficient, high-speed, and widespread telecommunications network. Countries that have invested in 5G networks, broadband, and data centers, such as South Korea and Finland, have seen a significant increase in their ICT exports. An effective infrastructure policy must include public and private investments, promote public-private partnerships, and ensure that even the most remote areas have access to modern technologies. In addition to infrastructure, human capital development is crucial. Digital skills are at the heart of developing a competitive ICT ecosystem. Governments must invest in technology-oriented educational programs, from primary school to university, focusing on advanced skills such as artificial intelligence, programming, data management, and cybersecurity. Countries like India, which has become a global hub for software and IT services, have adopted targeted educational policies to train a highly qualified workforce, creating technical institutes and universities specialized in the ICT sector. Moreover, continuous training and updating programs for already active workers can help maintain competitiveness in a rapidly evolving sector. Another key element is the creation of fiscal and financial incentives for ICT companies. Governments can introduce tax breaks for startups and technology companies, reducing tax rates or offering exemptions for the first few years of activity. Countries like Ireland have attracted global technology giants by offering a favorable tax regime, thereby creating a thriving ecosystem that has boosted ICT services exports. In addition to tax incentives, access to credit for ICT companies can be facilitated through public funds or loan guarantees, supporting the birth of new companies and the expansion of existing ones. Internationalization policies are equally crucial to increase the share of ICT exports. Access to foreign markets can be facilitated through bilateral or multilateral trade agreements that include specific provisions on digital services. The creation of specialized diplomatic and commercial networks aimed at promoting ICT services abroad can facilitate the entry of national companies into international markets. Countries like Singapore have implemented aggressive internationalization strategies, promoting their technological offering through trade missions and participating in international fairs. These strategies have allowed local companies to expand rapidly on a global scale. Effective digital governance is another pillar of economic policies for expanding ICT exports. Governments must create a clear and predictable regulatory framework that protects intellectual property, ensures cybersecurity, and facilitates digital transactions. A stable and transparent regulatory environment is essential for attracting foreign investment and stimulating the growth of ICT companies. Additionally, policies that promote transparency, system interoperability, and the protection of

personal data are fundamental for building consumer and business trust in digital services. Countries like Israel and Estonia, which have invested heavily in cybersecurity and digital governance, have seen significant growth in their ICT sector. Promoting innovation and research and development (R&D) is another important lever. Governments must encourage the creation of technology hubs and industrial clusters where companies, universities, and research centers can collaborate to develop innovative solutions. Public grant programs for research projects, incentives for collaboration between companies and universities, and the creation of technology parks are essential policies to stimulate innovation. For example, countries like Israel have created a favorable ecosystem for innovation, with support policies for research that have given rise to a vibrant startup sector. In parallel, it is necessary to promote digital entrepreneurship. Encouraging the creation of tech startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the ICT sector can expand the production base and increase exports. Policies that facilitate access to venture capital, accelerate startups, and simplify bureaucratic procedures can support the growth of new digital companies. Countries like the United States and the United Kingdom have benefited from a robust venture capital ecosystem and incubators that have fueled the growth of their technology industries and made them globally competitive. Finally, a policy of social cohesion and digital inclusion is essential to ensure that the benefits of growth in the ICT sector are spread equitably. The adoption of digital technologies must be accompanied by digital literacy programs that enable the entire population to actively participate in the digital economy. Digital inclusion not only improves social well-being but also expands the domestic demand for ICT services, which can then translate into greater international competitiveness. In summary, to increase the percentage of ICT services exports in total trade, it is necessary to adopt a holistic approach that integrates investments in digital infrastructure, human capital development, tax incentives, internationalization policies, strong digital governance, promotion of innovation, and support for entrepreneurship. Each country must adapt these policies to its specific context, but the common goal remains to create a favorable ecosystem for the growth of the ICT sector, which can drive the economy and improve its global competitiveness. The technological evolution requires that these policies be dynamic and flexible, capable of adapting to the rapid changes in the global digital market. Investing today in a well-defined strategic framework can bring long-term benefits, making ICT exports a driving force for stable and sustainable economic growth in the long run.

Conclusions. The value of ICT services exports as a percentage of total trade decreased on average between 2016 and 2022 by a value of -6.89%. Some countries have shown an above-average growth rate in ICT services exports as a percentage of total trade, such as Namibia with +1800.00%, Saudi Arabia with +1733.33%, Nigeria with +900.00%, Qatar with +577.78%, and Turkey with +466.67%. There are also countries that have recorded a value of ICT services exports as a percentage of total trade significantly below the average, namely Senegal with -73.73%, Nepal with -80.48%, Burundi with -82.62%, Benin with -89.44%, and Tajikistan with -95.92%.

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